

1 **Main complementary food ingredients contributing to aflatoxin exposure to infants and**
 2 **young children in Kongwa, Tanzania**

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9 **Abstract**

10 Complementary foods (CFs) provided to infants and young children (IYC) in sub-Saharan
 11 Africa contain ingredients that are susceptible to aflatoxin contamination. Chronic dietary
 12 exposure to aflatoxins is associated with health consequences. This study assessed the risk of
 13 exposure of IYC (6-12-month-old) in Kongwa, Tanzania to aflatoxins through CFs. The intake
 14 of aflatoxin susceptible flours (ingredients) in CFs by 35 IYC was estimated through multiple-
 15 pass 24-hr dietary recalls. Samples of the ingredients were tested for aflatoxins using High-
 16 Performance Liquid Chromatography. Exposure of a child to aflatoxins was estimated by a
 17 deterministic approach. The contribution of an ingredient to the overall exposure was estimated
 18 statistically. The key ingredients of CFs consumed by the IYC were maize, sorghum, pearl
 19 millet, rice, and groundnuts (pre-or post-blended with the other ingredients). Cereal and
 20 groundnut-based CFs were given as thin or stiff porridge. The average per capita daily intake
 21 of CFs was 89.45 g. About 82.14 % of the CF ingredients were contaminated with aflatoxin
 22 B1 (AFB1) in the range of 0.27 - 317 µg/kg, with a median of 3.96 µg/kg. AFB1 exposures
 23 ranged from 0.33 to 1168 ng/kg bw/day (median of 23.08 ng/kg bw/day). The Margins of
 24 Exposure were less than 10,000 for all the IYC, signifying a public health concern. Post-
 25 blended groundnut flour, followed by maize, contributed the most to the exposure of IYC to
 26 AFB1. Groundnut and maize used as CFs in Kongwa are likely to be the main contributors to
 27 the exposure of IYC to AFB1. Caregivers should be advised to replace maize and groundnuts
 28 with well-processed less susceptible cereals like pearl millet and other legumes, respectively.

29 ***Keywords:*** *Aflatoxins; Complementary feeding; Infants; Young Children; Dietary Exposure*

30 Declaration of Interests: None

Abbreviations

CFs	Complementary foods
IYC	Infants and Young Children
DNuO	District Nutrition Officer
IAC	Immunoaffinity column
FLD	Fluorescence detector
LODs	Limits of Detection
AFs	Aflatoxins
BMDL	Benchmark dose Lower Limit
MOE	Margin of Exposure
MMT	Mycotoxin Mitigation Trial

31 1. Introduction

32 Mycotoxins are low-molecular-weight toxic secondary metabolites synthesized by a variety of
33 fungal species such as *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, *Fusarium*, and *Alternaria* that colonize crops
34 in the field or post-harvest (Alshannaq & Yu, 2017; Cinar & Onbaşı, 2019). These toxins may
35 be found in food commodities, including cereal grains like sorghum, maize, pearl millet, rice,
36 and wheat (Chulze, 2010; Kimanya et al., 2008, 2014; Ojuri et al., 2018; Onyedum et al., 2020),
37 roots and tubers (Onyedum et al., 2020), nuts like peanuts or groundnuts (Fountain et al., 2015),
38 tree-nuts like pistachio, apricot kernels hazelnuts, almonds (Diella et al., 2018), spices
39 (Fundikira et al., 2020), and other food and feedstuff (EFSA, 2020). The presence of
40 mycotoxins in food crops is especially prevalent in tropical regions (Udomkun et al., 2017)
41 where the climatic conditions favor the proliferation of mycotoxin-producing fungi (Kumar et
42 al., 2008). According to the IARC (1993), apart from the hot and humid tropical climates,
43 aflatoxins (AFs) are also common in places where poor storage conditions facilitate the growth
44 of fungi and the subsequent production of toxins.

45 According to the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) (1993), aflatoxins (AFs)
46 which are mainly produced by *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus parasiticus* are the most
47 studied and detrimental mycotoxins. The main forms of these toxins are aflatoxin B1 (AFB1),
48 aflatoxin B2 (AFB2), aflatoxin G1 (AFG1), and aflatoxin G2 (AFG2). While *A. parasiticus*
49 can produce all types of AFs, *A. flavus* produces only AFB1 and AFB2 (Dorner 2008). The
50 AFs are classified as class I human carcinogens associated with liver cancer (IARC, 1993).
51 Kimanya et al. (2021) estimated that, in Tanzania, the population risk of aflatoxin-induced liver
52 cancer may be as high as 2.95 per 100,000 persons. Moreover, studies reported that AFB1 is
53 the most lethal, mutagenic, and carcinogenic (IARC, 1993; Raney et al., 1992) of all AFs.
54 Acute exposure to AFs can cause acute aflatoxicosis and ultimate death (Kamala et al., 2018;
55 Liu & Wu, 2020). Aflatoxins have also been linked to stunted child growth (Gong et al., 2002,
56 2003; Shirima et al., 2015; Turner, 2013), adverse birth outcomes (Turner et al., 2007), immune
57 system suppression (Jiang et al., 2005; Turner, 2013) and the interference of micronutrient
58 activity (Watson et al., 2016).

59 According to Chilaka and Mally (2020), the infants and young children (IYC) in sub-Saharan
60 Africa (SSA) are at a higher risk of exposure to AFs because of their routine consumption of
61 contaminated foods during complementary feeding (Gong et al., 2002; Kimanya et al., 2014;

62 Magoha et al., 2014, 2016) when breast milk can no longer meet their dietary needs (WHO,
63 2013). While several food products can be used as complementary foods (CFs), composite
64 flours typically made from starchy staples such as rice, maize, sorghum, and wheat which are
65 susceptible to contamination by AFs are the most accessible in developing countries (Alamu
66 et al., 2018). To improve their nutritional value, cereal-based CFs are normally mixed with
67 groundnuts which are also very susceptible to contamination by AFs (Magamba et al., 2017;
68 Makori et al., 2019; Mollay et al., 2020).

69 Of late, there has been extensive attention on the risks of exposure and the effects of
70 mycotoxins on IYC as the most vulnerable group. Like in other parts of SSA, several studies
71 have demonstrated the occurrence of chronic dietary exposure and co-exposure of IYC in
72 Tanzania to AFs and other mycotoxins (Anitha et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2018; Kamala et al.,
73 2018; Kimanya et al., 2014; Magoha et al., 2016; Makori et al., 2019; Shirima et al., 2015).
74 Yet, there are limited studies on the contribution of key ingredients in CFs to the exposure of
75 IYC to AFs in Tanzania. The present study was designed to estimate contribution of the main
76 CF ingredients to aflatoxin exposure among the IYC in Kongwa district. Additionally, the
77 study was conducted as part of a formative research to inform the design of an IYC feeding
78 intervention as part of a cluster-randomized controlled mycotoxin mitigation trial (MMT) in
79 the district. Specifically, the study informed the MMT of the key ingredients used in CF in
80 Kongwa and the contribution of each in AF exposure among IYC feeding.

81 **2. Materials and Methods**

82 **2.1 Study Area**

83 The study was conducted in Kongwa District of Dodoma Region in Central Tanzania. The
84 district was purposively selected due to its high production and reliance on crops like maize
85 and groundnuts which are highly susceptible to contamination by AFs as staple foods. In
86 addition, these crops were easily accessible in the study area due to the presence of an
87 international maize and groundnuts market in the district. Four villages, namely Mtanana A,
88 Pandambili A, Sagara, and Machenje were purposively selected. The information on maize
89 production and consumption in Kongwa was provided by the District Agricultural Irrigation
90 and Cooperative Officer and the District Nutrition Officer (DNuO).

91 **2.2 Study Design**

92 This study was part of the formative research that used the Trials of Improved Practices
93 methodology (Dickin & Griffiths, 1997). Data were collected in two point visits. In the first
94 visit, mother-child (6 - 12 months of age) pairs were randomly enrolled from a list of eligible
95 children obtained from the register of the Reproductive and Child Health clinics at the health
96 facilities in each of the four villages. Mothers who were willing to participate in the study and
97 whose children were healthy and feeding/swallowing food normally were included in the study.
98 In total, 36 mother-child pairs consented and were enrolled to participate in the study. The
99 enrolment and data collection were performed between mid-February and early March 2018,
100 approximately 6 - 9 and 10 - 11 months after the harvesting of maize and groundnuts,
101 respectively. This timing was scheduled to account for contamination of food ingredients with
102 AFs during storage.

103 **2.3 Survey of complementary food intake**

104 A multiple-pass 24-hr dietary recall, as described by Gibson & Ferguson (2008) was used to
105 collect information on the intake of CFs and estimate the food intake of the IYC with minor
106 modifications. The protocol describes procedures for preparation and instructions for
107 interviewing. These include preparations of all required equipment (such as dietary weighing
108 scales, standard measuring cups, spoons, recall forms) and familiarization with staple foods of
109 the study area before embarking on the 24-hr interaction with participants. The steps for
110 conducting the 24-hr recall comprised of multiple (four) passes. Passes 1 and 2 of the 24-hr
111 recall interview were used to generate a list of the foods and drinks consumed by the targeted
112 child in the previous 24 hr at various times. Pass 3 described the foods consumed and showed
113 the recipes used during which the household kitchen utensils such as cups, bowls, spoons used
114 by the mothers/caregivers were used to measure the actual foods or water to show the weights
115 or volumes of ingredients used in the recipes of CFs. The researchers converted the amounts
116 into weight and volume equivalents by using calibrated measurements. Pass 4 narrated the
117 portion/size of food consumed by the children. Direct weighing was used to measure the
118 portion/size of stiff porridge consumed, in grams. The respondents used their cups to estimate
119 the volume of thin porridge consumed, using water. The volume was then converted to volume
120 equivalents (mL), using standard measuring cups. To ensure the correct measure of the
121 consumed portions or sizes, the respondents were asked to eliminate the leftovers; thus, the
122 final portions consumed by IYC were the ones measured by the researchers. The 24-hr dietary
123 recall questionnaire was administered repeatedly at two-point visits at an interval of 10 days.

124 **2.4 Bodyweight data**

125 The weight of each child was recorded as indicated in their Reproduction and Child Health
126 cards, during the period of data collection, for the computation of their dietary exposures to
127 AFs.

128 **2.5 Sampling of ingredients of CFs**

129 From each of the 35 families, samples of the susceptible foods consumed by an infant in the
130 past 24 hr were collected. Thus, food samples were collected at the time of each 24-hr recall
131 based on what the child ate according to the recall, for the analysis of AFs. About 250-500 g
132 of each sample was collected depending on the stock and amount each household was willing
133 to offer. If a household had less than 1 kg of a required foodstuff, a request was made for a
134 sample of about 250 g only. In cases where groundnut powder or *pre-blended* flour was used
135 in the CFs and only small quantities of it were available in the households, a sample of about
136 100 g was collected. A food collection form was used to guide the enumerators on the
137 procedures for sampling cereal grains and groundnut-based CFs. Each sample was thoroughly
138 mixed by inverting the storage bag up and down vigorously about five times and samples drawn
139 from different parts of the bag and mixed thoroughly before drawing the amount required as a
140 representative sample. Information about the source (market or home farm) of the cereal grains
141 and groundnuts that were used in CFs were also collected. Each sample was then separately
142 coded and kept in a clean Ziplock bag. During packing, all air inside the Ziplock bag was
143 squeezed out, and the bag was tightly zipped and stored in a refrigerator at 4°C at the Kongwa
144 District Hospital before being transported to the Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science
145 and Technology (NM-AIST) laboratory in Arusha for analysis.

146 **2.6 Extraction, clean up, and aflatoxin detection**

147 The content of each Ziplock bag was mixed thoroughly for 3 min using a laboratory mixer.
148 The determination of AFs in the sample was performed using the method described by Stroka
149 and Anklam (2000). About 25 g of the evenly-mixed sample was homogenized in a blender jar
150 at a high speed for 3 min with 100 mL of water/methanol in the ratio of 4:6 (v/v) for maize,
151 pre-blended, pearl millet, rice, and sorghum flours or 2:8 (v/v) for groundnut samples. The
152 difference in water : methanol ratio (Stroka & Anklam 2000; Cole & Dorner 1994) is due to
153 the complex matrices of protein and fat in groundnut (Zhao et al., 2012) that require more
154 methanol to extract AFs. The extracts were then filtered using filter papers (Whatman No. 1)

155 and 4 mL of each filtrate diluted with 8 mL of phosphate buffer saline at pH 7.3 (Sigma
156 Aldrich). The diluted extracts were loaded into the immunoaffinity column (IAC) [VICAM,
157 USA], topped with a syringe barrel, and fixed onto a vacuum manifold. The extract was allowed
158 to pass through at a flow rate of 3 mL per min. The IAC was then rinsed twice with 10 mL of
159 distilled water and a vacuum pump was applied to ensure that the solvent and water content
160 were drained to completion.

161 The bounded AFs were eluted from the IAC with 1 mL of acetonitrile (Sigma Aldrich) to an
162 amber vial. During this process, acetonitrile was left onto the column for a few seconds before
163 elution to allow for intensive contact with the adsorbent pad to detach the bound toxins. About
164 400 μ L of the eluted extracts were thoroughly mixed with 600 μ L of a derivatizing reagent
165 prepared from acetic acid, trifluoroacetic acid, and water in the ratio of 1: 2: 7 (v/v/v). The
166 mixture was then conditioned at 65°C for 15 min on a water bath and allowed to cool at room
167 temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) before injecting 10 μ L of each sample into the High-Performance
168 Liquid Chromatography system (Shmadzu, Japan) connected to a fluorescence detector (FLD)
169 (RF-20A Shimadzu, Japan) for the determination of AFs B1, B2, G1, G2. The mobile phase
170 was composed of acetonitrile, methanol, and water in the ratio of 1: 4: 5 (v/v/v) at a flow rate
171 of 1 mL per min. The FLD was set at 450 nm for the emission wavelength and 365 nm for the
172 excitation wavelength. The reverse-phase C18 column (250 x 4.6 mm) [Phenomenex, USA]
173 was used at a temperature of 40°C.

174 The suitability of the AF determination method was tested by spiking maize, *pre-blended*,
175 groundnut, pearl millet, rice, and sorghum flours with a standard mix/solution of AFs (B1, B2,
176 G1, G2) at three different concentrations of 0.5, 1 and 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. Those values were previously
177 used to (Kimanya et al., 2014, Magoha et al., 2016) and found appropriate to test the ability of
178 this method to detect AFB1 concentrations below the ML of 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ set by the EU for AFB1
179 in foods. Results of the recoveries are as indicated in Table S1.

180 The LOD was calculated as described by Sengul (2016), using the formula that Limit of
181 Detection (LOD) = $3 * \text{SD} + \text{Bave}$ where SD = Standard deviation of the measurement; Bave
182 = Average concentration of the spiked sample. Therefore, the limits of detection (LODs) for
183 AFG2, AFG1, AFB2, and AFB1 were 0.28, 0.39, 0.27, and 0.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ respectively.

184 Intra-day precision was assessed by running a standard of 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ after every 10 samples for
185 50 samples analyzed in a day (Table S2) whereas inter-day precision was measured by running

186 standards at 5 levels (2, 5, 10, 15, and 20 µg/kg) for 2 consecutive days. These were done as
 187 checkpoints and the results showed no deviations.

188 **2.7 Estimation of the daily flour intake**

189 The estimates of dietary exposure of IYC to AFs in the present study was based on flours
 190 consumed in stiff/thick (*ugali*) or thin (*uji*) porridge only because they are not only susceptible
 191 to contamination with AFs but also, the most commonly and frequently consumed foods in the
 192 study area.

193 The proportion of flour as consumed through a thin or stiff porridge was computed based on
 194 Kimanya *et al.* (2014) who estimated that the flour content of thin and stiff porridge consumed
 195 in Tanzania is 17 and 36% (w/w), respectively. The weight in grams of the thin or stiff porridge
 196 prepared from either cereal only or cereal-groundnut-based flour as estimated from each of the
 197 two 24-hr recalls was used to estimate the average flour intake per day per child. Before
 198 calculating the amount of consumed flour, cooking and adjusting volumes and weights of the
 199 thin porridge enabled us to estimate its specific gravity to be 1.1 g/mL. Therefore, the volumes
 200 (mL) of the thin porridge were multiplied by the specific gravity (g/mL) to obtain their
 201 consumed weight in grams.

202 **2.8 Estimation of dietary exposure to aflatoxins**

203 The estimation of dietary exposure to AFs in the current study was based on AFB1 only because
 204 it is the most toxic and carcinogenic aflatoxin for which a reference Margin of Exposure
 205 (MOE, 10,000) for assessment of health risk is available. The dietary exposure of individual
 206 children to AFB1 was estimated by the deterministic approach (Equation 1) (JECFA, 2010).
 207 The estimated exposure of a child to AFB1 (ng/kg bw/day) was calculated as a sum of
 208 individual AFB1 exposures through different CF ingredients consumed by the child. Exposure
 209 through an ingredient was estimated by multiplying the daily intake of contaminated
 210 ingredients and the contamination of AFB1 level in the consumed food ingredient and dividing
 211 the result by the child's body weight.

$$212 \quad Z = \sum_i^n \frac{X_i Y_i}{W} \quad \text{(Equation 1)}$$

213 Where; Z stands for the child's estimated daily intake (ng/kg bw/day), X_i , the contamination
 214 level of AFB1 in food ingredient i ($i = 1 \dots, n$) measured in (ng/g), Y_i is the flour in grams
 215 consumed per day, and W is the child's body weight in (kg).

216 There was a case where two different samples of similar ingredients (maize) were taken from
 217 a single household during the same visit. This was because the child consumed CF prepared
 218 from similarly purchased maize, but one maize ingredient was milled as undehulled flour
 219 whereas the other maize ingredient was dehulled \Rightarrow soaked \Rightarrow dried \Rightarrow milled before use
 220 in preparation of CFs. The estimated contamination levels of AFB1 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) in maize on a
 221 particular day was calculated through adjustment whereby:

$$222 \quad X_i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^s a_k p_k}{\sum_{k=1}^s p_k} \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

223 X_i is the contamination level of AFB1 in food ingredient i ($i = 1 \dots, n$), a_k is the contamination
 224 level ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) of ingredient i present in k^{th} sample ($k=1 \dots s$), p_k is the amount consumed by a
 225 child (flour in kg) in k^{th} sample (Table S3).

226 It's also worth noting that, since we had the proportions of groundnuts and cereal in blended
 227 flour, the adjustment for AFB1 contamination level presented in post-blended flour was done
 228 by the following formula;

$$229 \quad X_i = \sum_{r=1}^n \omega_r a_r \quad (\text{Equation 3})$$

230 X_i , the adjusted contamination level of AFB1 in post-blended flour sample, a_r is the
 231 contamination level ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) of ingredient r present in post-blended flour, ω_r is the proportion
 232 of food ingredients used to prepare the post-blended flour (Table S4).

233 Descriptively, if a child consumed one kind of food ingredient during the two visits, the average
 234 consumption in g/day was multiplied by the average contamination level of AFB1 in the food
 235 ingredients in (ng/g) divided by the average child's bodyweight taken during the two visits.
 236 The summation of estimated daily intake was calculated when a child consumed (on the same
 237 day or different days) more than one kind of food ingredient, for example, maize-based thin
 238 porridge and pre-blended flour-based thin porridge, maize-based thin porridge, and sorghum-
 239 based stiff porridge or post-blended flour-based thin porridge and maize-based stiff porridge.
 240 Where AFB1 was not detected, samples were assigned a value half the LOD (EFSA, 2010).

241 **2.9 Estimation of the risk of exposure of public health concern**

242 The MOE was used to determine the level of risk of exposure to AFB1 per child. The MOE is
243 considered the best approach to characterize risks for genotoxic or carcinogenic substances
244 (Barlow et al., 2006; Benford et al., 2010; EFSA, 2020). The benchmark dose lower confidence
245 limit, BMDL₁₀ (for a benchmark dose-response of 10% for the incidence of hepatocellular
246 carcinoma in male rats following AFB1 exposure) of 400 ng/kg bw/day was used to calculate
247 MOE of each child to AFB1 (EFSA, 2020). EFSA used the animal experiments based BMDL
248 because the calculation of a BMDL from the human data was not appropriate (EFSA 2020). A
249 MOE of 10,000 which is equivalent to an exposure of 0.04 ng /kg bw/day (400 ng/kg bw/day
250 divided by 10,000) marked the cut-off point of low public health concern. This also implies
251 that exposure above 0.04 ng /kg bw/day or MOE < 10,000 is a public health concern (EFSA,
252 2020). Therefore, a child whose MOE was < 10,000 was considered at risk and represented a
253 public health concern.

254 **2.10 Groundnuts proportion in pre and post-blended flour.**

255 We estimated the fraction of groundnut ingredients present in pre-blended flour and post
256 blended flour by taking the groundnut amount in grams divided by the total amount of flour in
257 grams in the total blended flour. The amount of groundnuts used in pre-blended and post-
258 blended flour was estimated on a digital weighing scale using the weight equivalents provided
259 by the mothers/caregivers during the multiple pass 24-hr recall (pass three), using the actual
260 household kitchen utensils. In the case were water (mL) was used by caregivers to estimate the
261 amount of the missing ingredient, the amounts were converted to weight equivalents by
262 researchers using measurements of actual food by digital weighing scale, following 3
263 consecutive measurements, in which the average was taken as the amount of actual ingredient
264 in grams.

265 **2.11 Statistical analysis**

266 IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 26) was used for normality testing and descriptive data analysis.
267 The Shapiro-Wilk test showed that the datasets were skewed even after different
268 transformations, thus all further statistical analyses involved non-parametric tests. The
269 variables were analyzed with Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney rank tests for differences
270 among different subgroups. Correlations among scaled variables were tested by Spearman's

271 rank correlation test. Microsoft Excel (2016) was used for the computation of dietary exposure
272 to AFB1.

273 **3. Results and Discussion**

274 **3.1 Demographic information of participants**

275 The demographic information of the studied IYC is presented in Table 1. It is good to note that,
276 from the 36 enrolled mother- child pairs, 1 pair dropped out, leaving 35. The reason for
277 dropping out was not given. In total, there were 31 infants and 4 young children in the first
278 visit whereas in the second visit, the numbers changed to 24 and 11, respectively. The numbers
279 of infants decreased from 31 to 24 and of children increased by the same number, from 4 to 11,
280 because at visit 2, 7 subjects had transitioned from infancy to young childhood. The average
281 bodyweight of the infants was 8.9 and 8.94 kg in the first and second visits, respectively.

282 **3.2 Types and intake of complementary food flours**

283 The foods consumed by the IYC were stiff and thin porridges. Following the procedures
284 described by Kimanya et al. (2014) to convert stiff and thin porridge weights into amounts of
285 flour consumed, the daily average sum of flour consumption by a child was 89.45 g. Table S5
286 shows the type of each ingredient and the amount of intake per IYC per day. The daily intake
287 of flour of each ingredient per child was converted into energy intake in kcal using the Tanzania
288 food and composition tables (Lukmanji et al., 2008). Energy intakes in about 50 (50.77-196.31
289 kcal) , 90.9 (112.63-495.98 kcal) and 37.5 % (69.72-245.53 kcal) of the children had less than
290 the respective WHO recommended daily energy requirements of 200, 550, and 300 kcal for
291 age groups of 6 - 8, 12 - 23, and 9 - 11 months, in addition to breastmilk (WHO, 2009).

292 The types of cereal-only flour used to prepare CFs included maize, sorghum, rice, and pearl
293 millet. These flours were used to prepare thin or stiff porridges. The blended flours contained
294 one or more types of these cereals and groundnuts. In *pre-blended flour*, groundnuts were
295 mixed with maize or other cereal(s) before milling, while in post-blended flours, groundnut
296 powder was mixed with any of the cereal flours after milling (just before cooking). These flours
297 were solely used to prepare thin porridges. The proportion of groundnuts in pre-blended and
298 post-blended flour ranged from 0.000281 to 0.65 with an average of 0.25 (Table S6). There
299 was a strong and significant correlation between groundnuts proportions in the post and pre-
300 blended flour and the AFB1 contamination level ($r=0.5$, $p=0.02$). This implies that as

301 caregivers increased more groundnuts in the formulation of pre or post-blended flour, there
302 was an increase in the overall flour contamination levels.

303 Though serving as the main components of CFs owing to their excellent energy and nutritional
304 sources (Klerks et al., 2019), cereal ingredients are susceptible to mycotoxin contamination
305 which increases the risk of exposure to these toxins (Mollay et al., 2021).

306 Other CFs given to IYC in the present study were identified as roasted maize, vegetables in
307 form of green leaf vegetable relish, *mandazi*, *mamung'unya*, tea, *futari*, sweets, raw
308 groundnuts, potatoes, bread, beans relish, fruits (watermelon, ripe banana, mangoes). *Mandazi*
309 is normally made by deep-frying small pieces of wheat flour dough. *Mamung'unya* is a squash-
310 like fruit of a flowering plant grown in the study area during the rainy season (normally during
311 the maize production season) and is prepared by chopping the fruit into small pieces and boiling
312 the pieces in water with the addition of a small amount of salt to taste. *Futari* in this study, is a
313 boiled and mashed mixture of peeled *mamung'unya* with groundnut powder and small
314 amounts of oil, onion, and salt. Although, the consumed quantities of these foods are smaller
315 compared to the maize flour, or blended groundnut-based foods, the risk of exposure to
316 aflatoxins from them cannot be ignored. This suggests that interventions to minimize aflatoxin
317 exposure among IYC in Tanzania should also address minor ingredients of maize and
318 groundnuts origin.

319 **3.3 Aflatoxin contamination of complementary food ingredient flours**

320 In total, 84 samples of ingredients meant for the preparation of CFs were collected from
321 Kongwa district and AFB1 was present in 82.14% of all tested samples in the range of 0.27 to
322 317 µg/kg with a median of 3.96 µg/kg. We found that 53.62% of the collected samples had
323 AFB1 proportion at more than 50% of the total contamination by AFs. Previous studies
324 elsewhere have reported that AFB1 is the most toxic and frequently detected in aflatoxin-
325 contaminated samples, and its contribution is the largest in total (Adetunji et al., 2014; JECFA,
326 2017; Yabe & Nakajima, 2004). This calls for immediate intervention to IYC who consumed
327 groundnut and maize-based CFs, to reduce exposure to AFB1 and the related health effects
328 such as stunting. Ismail et al. (2021) argues that African countries require intervention
329 strategies that can mitigate early-life dietary exposure to AFs in foods to reduce the associated
330 health implications.

331 Most of the CFs studied in the present study were cereal-based which are among the most
332 susceptible foods to mycotoxin-contamination (Peraica et al., 2014). In a recent study in the
333 same district, samples of several cereal grains intended for porridge preparation were found to
334 be highly contaminated with AFB1 (mean 38.3 µg/kg; maximum 271 µg/kg) (Anitha et al.,
335 2020). These results are also consistent with those of Kimanya et al. (2014) from Rombo
336 district in Kilimanjaro region where the AFB1 contamination ranged from 0.53 to 364 µg/kg.
337 These results have also been replicated in other studies across Tanzania, for instance, in Rombo
338 district where 58% of 67 maize flour samples consumed by infants under the age of 6 months
339 had detectable AFs (range 0.33 - 69.47 µg/kg; median 6 µg/kg) (Magotha et al., 2016), and in
340 Kilosa, Hanang' and Rungwe districts where the levels of AFs in maize samples meant for the
341 preparation of CFs was found to range from 1.0 to 1081 µg/kg (Kamala et al., 2017). High
342 contamination levels ranging between 150 and 345 µg/kg have also been established for cooked
343 maize porridge samples collected from several villages in Kilimanjaro, Iringa, and Tabora
344 regions (Geary et al., 2016).

345 **3.4 Contribution of groundnuts to contamination in blended flours**

346 Groundnuts were contaminated with AFB1 with levels ranging from 0.55 to 317 µg/kg.
347 Groundnuts had the highest contamination levels with a median of 6.87 µg/kg compared to
348 cereals like maize (median 4.17 µg/kg) and pearl millet (median 1.45 µg/kg). Likewise, all
349 cereal-groundnut-based samples were contaminated with AFB1 (Table S6), suggesting that the
350 practice of mixing more than one cereal and/or groundnuts in composite flours may increase
351 the risk of exposure of IYC to AFs. The results also revealed that cereal-groundnut-based flour
352 formulations were the major contributors to exposure of IYC to AFB1 (Table S6). The study
353 by Makori et al. (2019) also attributed the high levels of AFB1 in composite flour to the
354 inclusion of groundnuts during their formulations. Similar findings have also been established
355 in studies conducted elsewhere in Tanzania (Anitha et al., 2017; Chen et al., 2018; Magembe
356 et al., 2016). The susceptibility of groundnuts to contamination by AFs has largely been linked
357 to the geocarpic nature of its pods which favors the growth of mycotoxigenic fungi
358 (Kachapulula et al., 2017; Waliyar et al., 2015).

359 **3.5 Maize and other cereals**

360 In the present study, 78.85 % of the maize samples were contaminated with AFB1 in the range
361 of 0.28 - 7.75 µg/kg (Table 2). Furthermore, the maize samples had the highest contamination

362 of AFB1 compared to other cereals with a median 4.17 µg/kg, followed by pearl millet samples
363 with a median of 1.45 µg/kg and sorghum (median 1.35 µg/kg). Unlike other cereals, maize
364 grains are larger and can promote infestation and subsequent contamination with AFs.
365 According to Benkerroum (2020), maize is the most highly and frequently aflatoxin-
366 contaminated crop in SSA. Although the range of maize contamination with AFB1 in the
367 present study (0.28 - 7.75 µg/kg) was lower than that of 0.85 - 55.73 µg/kg obtained by Magoha
368 *et al.* (2016) in Rombo District, the proportion (78.85 %) of maize flour contaminated with
369 AFB1 in the present study exceeded that established by Magoha *et al.* (2016) who reported that
370 only 50.75% of the samples were contaminated with AFB1. Unlike the present study that was
371 done in central Tanzania (Kongwa), the study by Magoha *et al.* (2016) was conducted in
372 northern Tanzania (Rombo), thus the climatic differences between the two study locations may
373 account for the differences observed regarding the contamination of maize with AFB1.

374 Even though only one sample of rice was tested and found contaminated with AFB1 and total
375 AFs at 0.27 and 2.34 µg/kg, respectively, this implies that rice is susceptible to contamination
376 with AFs. Various studies from other countries in the world like Austria (Reiter *et al.*, 2010),
377 Iran (Mazaheri, 2009), China (Lai *et al.*, 2015), Vietnam (Nguyen *et al.*, 2007), and Pakistan
378 (Iqbal *et al.*, 2016) have reported AFs contamination of rice. Compared to maize and
379 groundnuts, low levels of contamination by AFB1 (1.44 - 1.47 µg/kg) and total AFs (2.69 -
380 7.26 µg/kg) were also established for pearl millet. Other studies in SSA have also established
381 low levels of contamination of pearl millet by AFs, for instance, 0.14 – 6.4 µg/kg in Kenya
382 (Sirma *et al.*, 2015), and 1.12 µg/kg in Ethiopia (Chala *et al.*, 2014).

383 **3.6 AFB1 contamination levels above Maximum limit**

384 Levels of AFB1 for 78.57 and 48.78 % of the groundnut and maize samples, respectively,
385 exceeded the maximum limit (ML) of 5 µg/kg set for groundnuts and maize flours intended for
386 human consumption in Tanzania (EAC, 2011; TBS, 2014a; TBS, 2014b) (Table 2). These
387 proportions of samples exceeding the regulatory limits are also greater than those observed by
388 Magoha *et al.*, (2016) in Rombo District in Northern Tanzania where only 35.29% had AFB1
389 > 5 µg/kg. Similar findings have also been reported by Makori *et al.* (2019) where about 30%
390 of infants in Dodoma, Tanzania were found to consume CFs with AFs above the ML. Other
391 studies have also found high concentrations of mycotoxins above the ML in foods meant for
392 IYC in SSA countries like Nigeria (Chilaka *et al.*, 2016) and Burkina Faso (Ware *et al.*, 2017).
393 Unfortunately, Tanzania has not yet set MLs for aflatoxins in foods for IYC. The contamination

394 levels determined in the CF ingredients were compared with, the ML of 0.10 µg/kg set by the
395 European Union for AFB1 in baby foods (European Commission, 2010). All the contaminated
396 CFs in this study had AFB1 levels above the EU ML. This signifies that, there is need for
397 Tanzania to set MLs for aflatoxins in CFs, monitor the ML to ensure compliance and take any
398 other appropriate interventions to minimize aflatoxin health risk among IYC in Kongwa and
399 Tanzania at large.

400 The current study showed that of all the samples where AFB1 exceeded the ML, 70 and 85%
401 of groundnuts and maize respectively were sourced from markets. This observation contradicts
402 reports by Lewis et al. (2005) which previously established that home-grown foods are more
403 prone to contamination with AFs than market-purchased ones. This is probably because, unlike
404 market-sourced cereals where one can access multiple types of cereals from different sources,
405 reliance on home-grown food may not allow access to multiple types of cereals that are mixed
406 to obtain a composite flour due to different production cycles. The practice of mixing multiple
407 portions of cereal to form composite flour has been found to increase the likelihood of
408 contamination with AFs in the current study as in previous ones (Blankson & Mill-Robertson,
409 2016; Kimanya et al., 2014). In a study done in Kenya, the higher proportion and levels of
410 contamination in market-sourced food samples with AFs compared to homegrown ones was
411 also attributed to the aggregation of cereal stock from different sources which can promote
412 cross-contamination and increase contamination levels (Kang'ethe et al., 2017). Moreover,
413 longer storage has previously been associated with a significant increase in contamination of
414 cereals by AFs (Liu et al., (2006), as may be the case with market-purchased samples.

415 **3.7 The risk of exposure to Aflatoxins**

416 The dietary exposure to AFB1 estimated in the current study ranged from 0.33 to 1168 ng/kg
417 bw/day with a median of 23.08 ng/kg bw/day. Consequently, the estimated MOE for IYC in
418 the present study ranged from 0.34 to 1212 with a median of 17. This implies that all IYC
419 (100%) were exposed to AFB1 above 0.04 ng/kg bw/day with a MOE < 10,000, indicating
420 that they are all a cause of public health concern (Barlow et al., 2006; EFSA, 2020). The
421 estimated dietary exposure to AFB1 per ingredient of CFs for IYC is indicated in Table 3. The
422 estimated dietary exposure to AFB1 for IYC was mainly contributed to by a combination of
423 maize and post-blended flour ingredients for which the highest exposure of 1168 ng/kg bw/day
424 was estimated in this study.

425 The maximum dietary exposure of AFB1 was slightly higher for young children (1168 ng/kg
426 bw/day) than for infants (418 ng/kg bw/day) but the difference was not statistically significant
427 ($p = 0.86$). On the other hand, a higher risk of exposure to AFB1 was determined for cereal-
428 groundnut-based CFs consumed by 60% of children compared to maize only-CFs consumed
429 by 31.40% of the children, and the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.33$).

430 More research is, therefore, necessary to inform on the contribution of groundnuts to the
431 exposure of IYC to AFs through CFs. The monotonous consumption of groundnut and maize-
432 based CFs which are susceptible to mycotoxin contamination could have promoted the
433 exposure of IYC to AFs (Ruel, 2003). Dietary exposures of IYC to AFB1 have also been
434 reported in other parts of SSA, for instance, in the range of 2.5 to 51,192 ng/kg bw/day in
435 Nigeria (Ojuri et al., 2018). The dietary exposure of IYC to AFB1 in this study was of public
436 health concern. This could be because the mothers mostly purchased the ingredients for CFs,
437 that may have been stored for long and transported under various weather conditions from
438 various parts of the country, or used their ingredients which may have been stored for long
439 after harvest, both of which may have increased their risk of contamination by AFs, although
440 the difference in exposure between the sources was not statistically significant ($p = 0.60$). The
441 use of freshly harvested cereals for preparing CFs for children as opposed to long-term stored
442 cereals which are more prone to contamination by AFs may minimize the exposure of IYC to
443 AFs. This is in line with the observations by Liu et al. (2006) that the risk of exposure to AFs
444 increases with increased storage of food.

445 **3.8 Study Limitation**

446 We ignored the contribution of AFs from groundnuts that were consumed in raw form by the
447 IYC, which were added to *futari* and green leafy vegetables relish. Likewise, the current study
448 did not account for the contribution of groundnut powder to the exposure of IYC to AFs.
449 Similarly, there was no control concerning the quality of the bodyweights used and the study
450 relied on mothers' memories concerning what the children had eaten in the previous 24 hr.
451 Besides, there was the use of water to estimate the quantities of thin porridge consumed by the
452 infants which may not be accurate.

453 **4. Conclusions**

454 The CFs in Tanzania are mainly prepared in form of stiff or thin porridge. The key ingredients
455 of the complementary feeding porridge were flours of maize, sorghum, pearl millet, rice, pre-

456 blended flour, and post-blended flour (both pre and post blend are composite cereal-groundnuts
457 mix differed in formulation process). The average sum of a complementary flour consumption
458 ranged from 14.02 to 198.22 g/child/day with a grand average of 89.45 g/child/day. These
459 ingredients are susceptible to contamination with AFs. In the present study, the contamination
460 of key ingredients of CFs, and the consumption and exposures of IYC to AFB1 were of public
461 health concern. A higher risk of exposure to AFs was estimated for IYC who consumed
462 groundnut-based CFs, followed maize-based foods compared to other cereal CFs. These results
463 suggest that IYC in the study area may be exposed to high levels of AFs, daily, due to
464 complementary feeding which calls for a fresh emphasis on tackling this problem. However,
465 more research is necessary to account for the contribution of groundnuts to the exposure of
466 IYC to AFs through CFs given the fact that our study considered a few households and was
467 only conducted in Kongwa. The exposure of IYC to AFB1 in this context was likely a result
468 of the repeated consumption of cereal-groundnut-blended flours in CFs. Perhaps, the best way
469 to reduce the risk of exposure to AFs in this context will be through diet diversification and the
470 replacement of maize and groundnuts with locally available foods such as pearl millet and
471 legumes that are less prone to contamination with AFs. This implies the need for stakeholders'
472 efforts in providing training to mothers of IYC and the community at large on the proper
473 processing of pearl millet and legumes like common beans to remove the anti-nutritional
474 factors and raise awareness on mycotoxin control to improve the nutritional value and safety
475 of CFs to IYC.

476

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495 **CRedit author contribution statement**

496 Clara Mollay: Conceptualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft,
497 Writing - review & editing, Visualization. Martin Kimanya: Conceptualization, Supervision,
498 Writing - review & editing. Neema Kassim: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing - review
499 & editing. Rebecca Stoltzfus: Conceptualization, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

500

501

502 **Ethical clearance**

503 The ethical approval for this study was obtained from the Tanzania National Institute for
504 Medical Research (NIMR), documents number NIMR/HQ/R8a/Vol.IX/2874 and
505 NIMR/HQ/R.8c/Vol.I/951. Before data collection, mothers/caregivers of eligible IYC signed
506 written informed consents. For mothers who could not read and write, researchers read the
507 informed consent statement to them and provided them with a stamped ink to sign with their
508 thumbs, if they agreed. The permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Kongwa
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798 **Table 1: Demographic information of the subjects**

Variable	Visit 1		Visit 2	
	n	%	n	%
Sex				
Male	19	54.3	19	54.3
Female	16	45.7	16	45.7
Age in months				
6-11	31	88.6	24	68.6
12 and above	4	11.4	11	31.4
Weight in Kgs				
7-7.9	8	22.9	7	20
8-8.9	8	22.9	10	28.6
9-9.9	12	34.3	11	31.4
10-10.9	6	17.1	6	17.1
11-11.9	1	2.9	1	2.9

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801 **Table 2: The occurrence of aflatoxin B1 and total aflatoxin in complementary flours above**
 802 **recommended maximum limits for Tanzania.**

Aflatoxin	Ingredients	Households (n=35)	No. of samples	≥LOD n (%)	Range ≥LOD (µg/kg)	Median ≥LOD (µg/kg)	>ML n (%)
AFB1	Maize	35	52	41(78.85)	0.28-7.75	4.17	20(48.78)
	Groundnuts	14	15	14(93.33)	0.55-317	6.87	11(78.57)
	Pre-blended	8	9	100	0.67-6.48	1.45	2(22.22)
	Sorghum	4	5	2 (40)	1.33-1.36	1.35	0
	Pearl millet	1	2	100	1.44-1.47	1.45	0
	Rice	1	1	100	0.27	0.27	0
	Post-blended	15	NA	NA	0.69-103.04	4.73	6(40)
	Overall	35	84	69(82.14)	0.27-317	3.69	33(47.83)
Total AF	Maize	35	52	51(98.08)	0.28-14.91	7.51	17(33.33)
	Groundnuts	14	15	100	1.1-428.55	13.25	11(73.33)
	Pre-blended	8	9	100	2.29-18.97	5.3	2(22.22)
	Sorghum	4	5	4(80)	2.33-24.74	3.92	1(20)
	Pearl millet	1	2	100	2.69-7.26	4.98	0
	Rice	1	1	100	2.34	2.34	0
	Post-blended	15	NA	NA	1-133.04	5.43	7(46.67)
	Overall	35	84	82(97.62)	0.28-428.55	7.12	31(37.80)

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- *Total AFs is the sum of AFB1+ AFB2+ AFG1 + AFG2. The limit of detection (LOD) for aflatoxin B1 in the current study is 0.25µg/kg. The LODs for AFB2, AFG1, and AFG2 were 0.27, 0.39, and 0.28 respectively.*
 - *The maximum limit (ML) for aflatoxin B1 and total AFs in groundnuts and cereal flours intended for human consumption are 5µg/kg and 10µg/kg respectively (EAC, 2011; TBS, 2014a; TBS, 2014b)*
 - *NA stands for not applicable since the post blended flours were not directly tested in the laboratory, only the materials (groundnuts + maize or sorghum) formulated it were tested, and the AFs were adjusted as per equation 3 and Table S4.*

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813

814 **Table 3: Ingredients of CFs and estimated daily intake as used in the AFB1 exposure**
 815 **assessment and the MOE results.**

S/N	Food ingredients	AFB1 Dietary intake (ng/kg bw/day)	MOE	Group
1	Maize	3.91	102	Young Children
2	Maize	15.90	25	Infants
3	Maize	41.97	10	Young Children
4	Maize	8.49	47	Infants
5	Maize	59.76	7	Young Children
6	Maize	8.14	49	Infants
7	Maize	23.39	17	Young Children
8	Maize	26.83	15	Infants
9	Maize	11.53	35	Young Children
10	Maize	122.64	3	Young Children
11	Maize	1.47	273	Young Children
12	Maize, Pearl millet	23.08	17	Infants
13	Maize, post-blended	5.52	73	Infants
14	Maize, post-blended	58.91	7	Infants
15	Maize, post-blended	29.92	13	Infants
16	Maize, post-blended	30.89	13	Young Children
17	Maize, post-blended	58.62	7	Infants
18	Maize, post-blended	117.83	3	Infants
19	Maize, post-blended	1167.55	0.34	Young Children
20	Maize, post-blended	418.45	0.96	Infants
21	Maize, post-blended	23.06	17	Young Children
22	Maize, post-blended	18.42	22	Infants
23	Maize, Pre-blended flour	27.90	14	Infants
24	Maize, Pre-blended flour	139.49	3	Infants
25	Maize, Pre-blended flour	15.76	25	Infants
26	Maize, Pre-blended flour	6.18	65	Young Children
27	Maize, Pre-blended flour	9.11	44	Infants
28	Maize, Pre-blended flour	47.66	8	Infants
29	Maize, rice, Pre-blended flour	14.36	28	Infants
30	Maize, sorghum	66.86	6	Infants
31	Maize, Sorghum, Post-blended flour	27.26	15	Infants
32	Maize, Sorghum, Post-blended flour, Pre-blended flour	17.50	23	Infants
33	Post-blended	0.33	1212	Infants
34	Post-blended	4.70	85	Infants
35	Sorghum	8.94	45	Infants

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817 *The estimated dietary AFB1 exposure ranged from 0.33-1168 ng/kg bw/day with a median of 23.08*818 *ng/kgbw/day.*

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824 **Appendix A: Supplementary tables**

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827 **Table S1: Aflatoxin recoveries**

Aflatoxin	Spiking concentration levels ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Percent recovery (%)					
		Maize	Groundnuts	Rice	Pearl millet	Sorghum	Pre-blended flour
AFG2	0.5	122.00	100.00	123.40	106.12	116.67	87.49
	1	102.26	107.20	118.90	119.99	80.24	115.95
	2	84.90	80.05	89.45	78.05	115.72	120.32
AFG1	0.5	121.00	80.83	122.00	107.40	114.94	85.77
	1	103.40	68.22	119.10	101.80	84.07	104.09
	2	93.95	85.31	82.55	80.05	87.63	119.94
AFB2	0.5	114.59	96.55	116.85	118.35	80.10	103.51
	1	103.59	95.78	124.63	107.08	106.55	106.38
	2	101.43	103.69	82.66	79.64	109.02	120.08
AFB1	0.5	122.00	95.42	115.55	108.12	119.29	89.46
	1	101.00	100.21	117.48	92.47	113.95	116.73
	2	80.54	104.76	89.59	79.38	111.27	123.27
Total AF	0.5	119.90	93.20	119.45	110.00	107.75	91.56
	1	102.56	92.85	120.03	105.33	96.20	110.78
	2	90.20	93.45	86.06	79.28	105.91	120.90

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829 *The AFs background values in blank samples ranged from 0.00 (maize) to 0.73 (pre-blended flour) and this was*
 830 *controlled in determination of recovery.*

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832 **Table S2: Intra-day Comparison ($5\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)**

Aflatoxin	Day 1					Day 2		
	Batch 1	batch 2	batch 3	Batch 4	batch 5	Batch 1	Batch 2	Batch 3
G2	4.94	4.88	4.94	5.15	4.89	5.05	4.83	4.91
G1	4.94	4.88	4.94	5.00	5.13	4.94	5.26	4.95
B2	5.07	4.99	5.07	4.95	4.98	4.82	4.92	4.95
B1	5.04	5.00	5.04	5.01	4.88	4.94	5.18	4.82
Total	19.99	19.75	19.99	20.11	19.87	19.74	20.18	19.63

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835 *Table S3: Adjustment of AFB1 in similar ingredients taken on the same day.*

Household	Ingredient	Sample 1		Sample 2		Adjusted AFB1 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)
		AFB1 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Amount consumed (g)	AFB1 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Amount consumed (g)	
19	Maize	0.360	28.8	0.805	18	0.531

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838 *Table S4: Adjusted AFB1 for post-blended flour*

Household	Visit	Post-blended flour Ingredients	Groundnuts (grams)	Maize (grams)	Groundnuts fraction in blended flour	Maize/sorghum fraction in blended flour	AFB1 in groundnuts ($\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$)	AFB1 in maize/sorghum ($\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$)	Amount consumed (grams)	Adjusted AFB1 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$)
7	1	Groundnuts	60	854	0.066	0.934	0.907	0.125	14.025	0.18
		Maize								
8	2	Groundnuts	12	32	0.273	0.727	6.806	0.313	18.326	2.08
		Maize							13.838	
9	1	Groundnuts	9	32	0.220	0.780	8.794	0.917	49.742	2.65
		Maize								
11	1	Groundnuts	69	38	0.645	0.355	6.432	6.459	24.31	6.44
		Maize								
16	1	Groundnuts	250	1000	0.200	0.800	0.156	0.125	57.035	0.13
		Maize								
17	1	Groundnuts	40	49	0.449	0.551	13.112	0.125	38.335	5.96
		Sorghum								
17	2	Groundnuts	36	83	0.303	0.697	7.177	0.309	15.895	2.39
		Maize								
22	2	Groundnuts	23	43	0.348	0.652	1.856	0.125	54.23	0.73
		Maize								
24	2	Groundnuts	40	48	0.455	0.545	11.443	4.166	38.335	7.47
		Maize								
26	2	Groundnuts	0.018128	64.5	0.000	1.000	7.273	7.753	87.89	7.75
		Maize								
27	2	Groundnuts	440	1040	0.297	0.703	297.709	1.640	110.33	89.66
		Maize								
32	2	Groundnuts	29	61	0.322	0.678	316.998	1.324	36.465	103.04
		Maize								
34	2	Groundnuts	12	45	0.211	0.789	5.703	2.920	46.75	3.50
		Maize								
36	2	Groundnuts	6	52	0.103	0.897	0.547	0.125	27.115	0.17
		Maize								

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840 *LOD for AFB1 = 0.25*841 *The contamination level below the limit of detection (undetectable) was set to LOD/2 of the AFB1 that was*
842 *0.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.*

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845 *Table S5: Types and consumption patterns for complementary foods*

Household	Ingredients	Source	Ingredient in blended flour	Total flour consumed (g)
1	Maize	Market		46.04
2	Maize	Market		32.94
3	Maize	Market		88.35
4	Maize	Market		67.83
5	Maize	Market		67.00
6	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	14.03
7	Maize	Market		25.50
	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	18.33
8	Maize	Market		46.75
	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	49.74
9	Maize	Market		19.26
10	Maize	Market		22.95
	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	24.31
11	Maize	Market		73.52
	Sorghum	Market		36.36
12	Sorghum	Market		106.18
13	Pre-blended flour	Home grown	Maize +groundnuts	63.92
	Maize	Home grown		60.29
14	Maize	Market		149.60
	Pre-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	48.62
15	Pre-blended flour	Home grown	Maize +groundnuts +sorghum	19.55
	Sorghum	Home grown		19.55
	Maize	Home grown		18.72
	Post-blended flour	home grown	Maize +groundnuts	57.04
16	Sorghum	Home grown		73.44
	Maize	Market		43.56
	Post-blended flour	Home grown	Sorghum +groundnuts	38.34
	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize+ groundnuts	15.90
17	Pre-blended flour	Home grown	Maize +groundnuts	50.15
	Maize	Market		23.4
	Rice	Market		32.64
18	Maize	Home grown		62.99
19	Maize	Home grown + market ^a		89.16
20	Pear millet	Market		28.05
	Maize	Home grown		20.52
21	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	54.23
22	Maize	Market		42.73
	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	54.23
23	Maize	Market		28.05
	Post-blended flour	Home grown + market ^b	Maize + groundnuts	38.34
24	Pre-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	107.10
	Maize	Home grown		73.80
25	Maize	Market		65.25
	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	87.89
26	Maize	Market		19.44
	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts	110.33
27	Maize	Market		29.47

28	Pre-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts +rice	35.38
	Maize	Home grown		31.68
29	Pre-blended flour	Market	PRUP (KIBOKO)	37.4
	Maize	Market		12.24
30	Maize	Market		22.32
	Post-blended flour	Market	Maize + groundnuts	36.47
31	Maize	Market		62.28
	Pre-blended flour	Market	Maize +groundnuts +rice +millet	73.95
32	Maize	Home grown + market ^c		40.78
	Post-blended flour	Home grown	Maize + groundnuts	46.75
33	Maize	Market		184.89
34	Maize	Home grown + market ^d		48.59
	Post-blended flour	Home grown + market ^e	Maize + groundnuts	27.11
35	Maize	Market		105.50

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847 *a. Maize was sourced from purchased and home grown during visit one and visit two respectively.*848 *b. Groundnuts was purchased while maize was from home grown. .*849 *c. Maize was purchased while groundnuts was from home grown.*850 *d. Maize was from home grown during visit one and purchased during visit two.*851 *e. Maize was sourced from home grown during visit one and purchased during visit two.*852 *PRUP: Purchased Ready to Use Pre- blended flour (namely KIBOKO). The PRUP was the only purchased*853 *blended flour, the rest were homemade by mothers/caregivers.*854 *The rice, pearl millet, pre, and post-blended flours were used to prepare thin porridge only while maize and*855 *sorghum were used for preparing thin or stiff porridge.*

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882 **Table S6: Proportion of groundnuts in cereal-groundnuts mix flour**

Flour ingredients type	Groundnuts proportion	AFB1 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)
Post-blended flour	0.066	0.176
Post-blended flour	0.273	2.084
Post-blended flour	0.220	2.646
Post-blended flour	0.645	6.442
Pre-blended flour	0.250	3.156
Pre-blended flour	0.250	6.469
Pre-blended flour	0.250	6.485
Post-blended flour	0.200	0.131
Post-blended flour	0.303	2.386
Post-blended flour	0.449	5.962
Pre-blended flour	0.250	1.395
Post-blended flour	0.348	0.728
Post-blended flour	0.127	0.688
Post-blended flour	0.455	7.474
Pre-blended flour	0.250	1.453
Post-blended flour	<0.001 ^m	7.753
Post-blended flour	0.297	89.661
Pre-blended flour	0.200	0.996
Pre-blended flour	PRUP	1.616
Post-blended flour	0.322	103.041
Pre-blended flour	0.056	0.737
Post-blended flour	0.211	3.506
Post-blended flour	0.103	0.169

883 *Groundnuts proportional range (m-0.645)*884 *m= 0.00028098*885 *PRUP: Purchased Ready to Use Pre- blended flour (namely KIBOKO). .*

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